

ISSUES EFL TEACHERS ENCOUNTER IN TEACHING WRITING ONLINE TO INTERMEDIATE LEVEL OR IELTS STUDENTS

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Abstract: Writing is taught to children as they start school from the very first grade despite the fact it still has been difficult for teachers to teach writing to intermediate or IELTS candidates in both online and face-to-face atmosphere. Writing helps learners to express their ideas in the form of recounts, narratives, procedures, descriptive, news items, reports, analytical expositions, spoofs, explanations, discussions, and reviews in one's routine. Multiple factors prevent teachers from conducting their writing lessons online successfully. Since the COVID-19 outbreak, teaching online has become very common and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) of teachers has become an important talk topic. Research has proven that teaching online is a new method and not all teachers are familiar with it despite being it the fact, that teachers are getting acquainted with it and sooner it will be easier for teachers to teach and learners to learn online. Moreover, this article shed light on the key qualities of online teachers who intend to teach writing to intermediate level learners as well as IELTS candidates.

Keywords: Online teaching, IELTS, IELTS Writing, Teachers qualities, TPACK.

Introduction to teaching writing online:

Teaching writing even in a face-to-face class environment is a difficult task for almost all teachers. Teaching writing begins as early as the first grade when a learner starts attending school. Writing involves multiple life-changing events such as formal and informal exams, professional correspondences, academic research, career development and many more. *“there are numerous consequences that could have a significant impact on students' academic performance if they have a weak foundation in writing. Writing is not only important for improving academic performance, but it also helps with social and emotional development”* [1]. Teaching writing skills in English is one of the issues that teachers confront, and *the goal of teaching English writing is to make sure students are able to express their meaning in the interpersonal and transactional discourse, in the form of recounts, narrative, procedure, descriptive, news item, report, analytical exposition, spoof, explanation, discussion, and review in the context of everyday life”* [2]. One of the most important competencies that every English teacher should have is the ability to teach writing effectively [1]. In 2008, Massive Open Online Courses have emerged and ever since it became popular despite controversies and lately they have been used in teaching writing as well [3]. Despite teaching writing being considered challenging, teachers and learners are fortified in their determination to teach and learn writing using technological tools such as Web 2.0 or 3.0 in their classrooms [4].

Introduction to teaching writing to IELTS / intermediate level learners:

Learners' inability to write well in their routine may jeopardise their higher studies as well as future career prospects. Teaching writing to intermediate-level learners differs from teaching basic levels. According to the evaluation criteria of Cambridge on the IELTS test the writing

band descriptor [5], [6] defines a candidate to score up to band score 5 should address the task with inappropriate format with not clear overview of the task with lack of supporting data. As far as the tone of the writing of the candidate is concerned, it can be variable and sometimes inappropriate. While covering all aspects of the detail in the question, the key features and a tendency to follow specific details and general information in the key features. However, an intermediate-level learner who should be able to score band 7 should cover the requirements of the task, able to present the overview of the main trends, differences or stages as well as unambiguously present the personal stand point. Further the ability to state the purpose of the writing clearly with appropriate and consistent tone is a must. Besides being able to present the viewpoint, it is also important that the writer must be able to fully extend the idea and develop it.

Regarding Coherence and Cohesion of the writing basic candidates are expected to present information with some organisation but ignored overall progression. Use of cohesion devices can be inadequate, inaccurate or over-used whereas when it comes to intermediate learners, they must be able to logically organise information and ideas with evidence on clear progression throughout the writing as well as ability to use a range of cohesive devices appropriately is desirable. It is accepted for basic level learners to use limited range of vocabulary to express the task minimally adequately with noticeable errors in spelling and word formation that will make the reader difficult to understand the meaning. On the other hand, intermediate-level learners must be able to sufficient range of vocabulary to express the task precisely and be able to use less common lexical items with some understanding about style and collocation.

Grammar is another important aspect that differentiate the level of both these learners that intermediate level learners will be able to use a variety of complex structures or compound complex structures with frequent error-free sentences and have an awareness and control of grammar. Moreover, punctuation yet a few errors can be made unlike basic level learners use a limited range of structure like compound sentences yet frequent attempt to make complex sentences with less accuracy can be seen. Besides, there can be grammatical errors and punctuation may be faulty hence errors can cause trouble for readers to understand the whole idea perfectly.

Issues in teaching writing to intermediate groups online:

There are several difficulties related to technology and students' perception such as getting a proper network connection and the interest in learning English online [4]. Following are some major challenges in learning writing online such as, technical problems, lack of concentration, lack of student-student as well as student-teacher interaction, time management, meeting deadline in assignment submission, health problems like tired eyes, cataract and other health impacts, lack of real gain or understanding the lesson, inadequate motivation and motivational opportunities, psychological problems and socialisation skills, lack of collaborative learning prospects [7]. Besides motivation, disobedience, disinterest and kind of quality of leaners will make learning online yet tougher [8].

Teachers engaged in online teaching would understand the range of challenges from linguistic issues to technical issues. And they further signified that teachers' mind-set that *"Many experts believe that online teaching is entirely different from face-to-face teaching"*. Besides, *"Some*

instructors even believe that writing cannot be taught online for a group of classes as it is individual-centric and involves a person-specific process” [8]. It’s generally believed that not all teachers are competent enough to handle technological devices yet as their pedagogical proficiency is. Since Computer Aided Language Learning or Computer Mediate Language Instruction is relatively new in this domain there have been lack of experience and expertise among teachers. In online lessons and assessment, it was always difficult for teachers to decide which of the work that students submitted are original or copied. During assessment, some students have even copied articles from online sources and therefore they were personally much contented about their answers but in examiner’s point of view of was a plagiarised answer. When the discussion further continued it was noticeable that teachers conduct online teaching and assessment cannot prevent learners from copying answers from other sources but they can be determined through a plagiarism checker [9].

Since the Covid-19 outbreak online learning and teaching have become more expedient, common and rather inevitable. Considering each and every factor that hinders teaching writing online from both learners and teachers point of view, it is apparent that learners should be motivated and given awareness on the appropriate use of online learning resources. On top of that, teachers should be given training on the effective use of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) and therefore teachers would have a thorough knowledge on the use of TPACK and consequently, the lessons shall be more productive. School administration and authorities should take a pragmatic approach to deal with issues related to teaching writing online such as making the internet and necessary technological accessories available to conduct the lesson effectively. While teaching writing, students may probably not get sufficient opportunities for productive writing practices. Teachers should design various tasks, including diagram descriptions, essays, emails, and letters, plus assign students a Google Classroom or kind of platform to upload their writing on a regular basis.

Key qualities of online IELTS writing teacher

An effective teacher of IELTS writing who conducts lessons online should possess several key qualities in order to rest-assure productive learning experience for candidates. Maintaining an interactive teaching style by engaging in collaborative activities. This is particularly the hardest things in conducting teaching writing online. The teacher should undoubtedly be expertise in IELTS writing format. Thorough understanding about marking criteria and writing band descriptors (Task 1, Task 2, Academic module and General Training) is crucial. Teachers must have a wide knowledge about the challenges learners would face while attending online lessons. Teachers must have acquired enough technological proficiency with synchronous and asynchronous learning tools, virtual learning platform, Learning Management System, distance-learning tools and so on. Ability to plan and implement teaching methods and technique in a real-like setting is one of the most important skills of an IELTS trainer conduct writing lessons online, furthermore implemented lessons must be evaluated with appropriate assessment techniques to provide students with feedback. In both synchronous and asynchronous mode, adaptability to online teaching environment and being able to show flexibility to get control of teaching methodology and techniques according to learners’ need and students’ individual variation as well as comprehensive knowledge about cultural sensitivity are necessary. Teachers teach online should necessary have a life-changing

motivational skill in order to inspire and motivate learners to set goals and consequently achieve them. In addition, strong communication skills to explicitly impart complex lessons in an understandable and simple way. Moreover, teachers intend to teach online must be ready to develop their professional competencies as the technological tools and devices do upgrade [11].

Conclusion

The exorable growth of online learning and teaching have become an unescapable scenario in terms of modern TPACK integrated educational system. For the fact that teaching writing online is relatively a new approach, the consequences of the coronavirus resulted in a swift change in education for both students and academicians who were unprepared to face the change in place [10]. There are myriad issues of teaching writing online either synchronously or asynchronously. Teachers have challenges ranging from linguistic point of view as well as technical. Dealing with learners' differences and qualities online would yet be another hindrance. Teachers of Intermediate level or IELTS lessons should be able to well-versed in their key qualities to become an online teacher. Hence, know the use of online teaching and learning tools and be ready to be professionally developed themselves as the technology upgrades. To sum up the whole, despite challenges, there are high possibilities for making use of online resources in pedagogy more effectively and efficiently and therefore teachers should foresee the advantageous more than looking at the drawbacks and challenges.

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